

ISOLATION OF MICROORGANISMS INVOLVED IN THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF CELLULASE ENZYMES AND THEIR BIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. *In this study, the bioconversion efficiency of various fungal strains in the production of feed protein from lignocellulosic raw materials was investigated. Substrates prepared from corn stover and wheat bran were used as experimental materials and inoculated with Chaetomium globosum, Trichoderma asperellum, Trichoderma hamatum, and Penicillium canescens under solid-state fermentation conditions. The results demonstrated significant variation in the protein (biomass) production capacity among the fungal strains. The highest level of protein synthesis was recorded for Chaetomium globosum, reaching a maximum of 71.2 ± 2.87 mg/g. Trichoderma asperellum also exhibited high performance (59.3 ± 2.24 mg/g) and was distinguished by its strong enzymatic activity. Trichoderma hamatum showed moderate results (46.5 ± 2.17 mg/g), while Penicillium canescens demonstrated relatively lower values (40.3 ± 1.81 mg/g). Microbiological treatment significantly improved the chemical composition of corn stover: protein content increased, crude fiber decreased, and both energy value and mineral content were enhanced. The highest nutritional parameters were observed in substrates treated with Chaetomium globosum (protein 18.50%, energy 3182 kcal/kg). Trichoderma asperellum was characterized by balanced bioconversion properties, whereas Penicillium canescens, despite its high enzymatic activity, showed comparatively lower biomass production.*

Keywords: *lignocellulose, bioconversion, solid-state fermentation, feed protein, micromycetes, Chaetomium globosum, Trichoderma asperellum, Trichoderma hamatum, Penicillium canescens, enzymatic activity, biomass synthesis, corn stover, wheat bran, nutritional value, protein, biotechnology.*

Introduction

At present, the growing global demand for food and feed products—particularly the sharply increasing need for high-quality protein sources—necessitates the development of alternative and sustainable technologies. Due to the limitations of conventional protein sources, including plant- and animal-derived proteins, as well as the associated economic and environmental challenges, the search for new and efficient sources has become an urgent issue.

Cellulose is one of the most abundant polysaccharides in nature and constitutes the primary structural component of plant biomass. Despite its widespread availability, its complex structure limits its direct utilization by most organisms. The biodegradation of cellulose is carried out by a specialized enzyme complex—cellulases. This enzyme system includes endoglucanases, exoglucanases, and β -glucosidases, which synergistically hydrolyze cellulose into simpler sugars, predominantly glucose.

The resulting simple carbohydrates are assimilated by microorganisms and serve as sources of energy and carbon for their growth and development. Consequently, microbial cell biomass

increases and the process of protein biosynthesis is intensified. Thus, the utilization of cellulose-based substrates enables the production of high-protein microbial biomass—feed protein.

The activity of cellulase enzymes is one of the key factors determining the rate and efficiency of cellulose degradation, which in turn directly influences the level of protein synthesis by microorganisms. Therefore, investigating the properties of cellulases, the factors affecting their activity, and their role in microbial protein production is of significant scientific and practical importance.

This article analyzes the activity of cellulase enzymes in cellulose degradation and their role in the biosynthesis of feed protein by microorganisms.

Literature Review

Globally, the demand for livestock meat exceeds 420 million kg per day. The primary sources of animal protein have traditionally included various types of farm animals and poultry, as well as milk, eggs, fish, and fish products. For the optimal functioning of physiological and biochemical processes in the human body, the recommended annual consumption levels are 70–75 kg of meat products, 320–340 kg of milk and dairy products, 260 eggs, and 18–22 kg of fish and fish products [1].

A novel technology with the potential to reduce the environmental impact of protein production is fermentation-based “cellular agriculture,” in which microorganisms are utilized for the production of food products [2].

Most feeds used in livestock production do not contain sufficient amounts of protein and vitamins. Consequently, a significant deficiency of feed protein is observed in many countries. These shortcomings and challenges are primarily addressed by increasing the content of plant-derived proteins—particularly those present in grains—that are essential for animal nutrition [3].

Fungi are widely used in the production of valuable feed for ruminants (cattle). This is due to their ability to convert low-nutritional, and even non-proteinaceous substrates into protein by utilizing the nitrogen present in their composition, as reported in several studies. In addition, alternative plant biomass or concentrates can also be used as protein sources for ruminants [4].

In addition to proteins, microbial cells synthesize other valuable nutritional components, including easily digestible carbohydrates, lipids rich in unsaturated fatty acids, vitamins, as well as macro- and microelements [5].

The use of microorganisms enables the industrial-scale production of large quantities of feed concentrates within a limited area, irrespective of seasonal variations. Microbial cells are capable of synthesizing proteins from agricultural and industrial wastes and, at the same time, possess the ability to recycle these wastes, thereby contributing to environmental protection [6].

Microbial synthesis is characterized by a very rapid rate. For example, during the seed maturation stage, a soybean plant weighing 500 kg accumulates approximately 40 kg of protein per day, whereas a bull of the same weight produces only 0.5–1.5 kg, and 500 kg of yeast cells are capable of synthesizing up to 1.5 tons of protein. As sources of feed protein, various species of yeasts and bacteria, microscopic fungi, and unicellular algae are commonly utilized [7].

An important task is the search for active microbial strains capable of degrading lignin and exhibiting high resistance to microflora-mediated decomposition. At present, fast-growing fungal strains of the genera *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, and *Trichoderma* have been selected for industrial cultivation. These fungi consist of cells with relatively less rigid cell walls, a characteristic that positively influences the digestibility of mycelium and mycelium-based products [8].

Compared to yeast proteins, proteins of microscopic fungi are distinguished by a higher content of sulfur-containing amino acids and better digestibility. The concentration of nucleic acids in fungal mycelium (1–4% of dry weight) is nearly comparable to that of proteins in plant tissues. At the same time, fungal biomass contains relatively lower levels of protein (20–60% of dry weight) than yeasts, and their biomass grows at a comparatively slower rate. Lower filamentous fungi cultivated on cellulose- and lignin-containing plant wastes are capable of synthesizing complexes of hydrolytic enzymes, degrading cellulose and lignin into simpler compounds, and consequently producing amino acids and proteins [9].

The high digestibility of fungal protein in animals, along with its relatively low nucleic acid content, allows it to be used as a feed additive at significantly higher concentrations than feed yeast. Typically, fungal protein may be included at 15–20% of the total dietary protein when feeding young animals, and up to 50% in the rations of adult animals. To compensate for the shortage of protein raw materials, it is necessary to expand the use of secondary resources from the processing, food, microbiological, and chemical industries. This includes increasing the production of feed protein from plant residues and the rational utilization of fermentation by-products (molasses residues, brewer's grains, etc.), as well as wastes from the dairy and meat industries. It is also envisaged to utilize advances in biotechnology, particularly microbial synthesis products such as amino acids and feed yeast. Another important producer of feed proteins and enzymes is fungi of the genus *Trichoderma*. Currently, the most widely used method for commercial cellulase production is submerged cultivation (involving the preparation of inoculum followed by transfer into a nutrient medium). At the same time, surface cultivation provides more favorable conditions for the growth of aerobic microscopic fungi [10].

Currently, there are two principal approaches to the use of enzyme preparations in the feeding of agricultural animals: their direct inclusion in feed and the pre-treatment of feed with enzyme preparations. Since the main components of animal diets consist of plant proteins, cellulose, and starch-containing substances, the application of agents capable of degrading these components is considered appropriate. Enzymes such as proteases, amylases, and cellulases, as well as their complexes, hydrolyze proteins, starch, and fiber, thereby enhancing their digestibility and utilization by the animal organism. In livestock production, it is also advisable to employ enzymes synthesized by microorganisms inhabiting the animal gut. These enzymes are naturally selected and are capable of hydrolyzing dietary components incorporated into the ration [11].

Materials and Methods

Bioconversion processes of plant residues by selected micromycete strains were investigated. In studying the bioconversion of cellulose-containing plant raw materials, the enzymatic activity of selected micromycete strains (*Trichoderma asperellum* and *Chaetomium globosum*) was utilized. During the course of the study, enzyme complexes isolated from the culture liquids of these fungi were applied in the degradation of cellulosic substrates.

The fungal culture grown in a liquid nutrient medium was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes, and the mycelium was separated from the culture liquid. Under solid-state fermentation conditions, after completion of fermentation, either the entire mass of the culture medium or an aqueous extract obtained by pressing (filtrate) was used. In this process, the following ratio was applied: 10 units of cellulolytic activity per 1 g of treated substrate.

In developing the solid-state fermentation regime, pre-prepared aboveground biomass of amaranth and winter wheat straw were used as raw materials. These substrates were dried to a moisture content of 6–7% and subsequently ground to a particle size of 1.5–2.0 mm.

Fermentation under laboratory conditions was carried out in 1 L conical flasks. Under semi-industrial conditions, cultivation was performed in special trays measuring 30×40 cm, with a substrate layer not exceeding 50–55 mm in height. The nutrient medium was prepared based on the composition described by Mandels [12], consisting of ground wheat (50%) and amaranth biomass (50%), or straw moistened with a mineral medium. The initial pH was maintained within the range of 4.7–4.9.

During the enzymatic hydrolysis process, 10 mL of water was added per 1 g of substrate, and the mixture was heated to 100°C and boiled for 5 minutes. It was then cooled to room temperature, after which culture liquid with an enzymatic activity of 10 units per 1 g of substrate was added. The mixture was maintained at 29–33°C and continuously agitated at 150 rpm.

The efficiency of bioconversion was evaluated based on the amount of reducing sugars formed as a result of the degradation of cellulosic substrates. The determination of reducing sugars was carried out using Müller's alkaline solution. This method is based on the reduction of Cu²⁺ ions to Cu₂O under the influence of reducing substances. The resulting product was treated with an iodine solution, and the excess iodine was quantified by titration with sodium thiosulfate solution [11].

The protein content was determined using the Lowry method. In order to optimize the microbiological degradation of lignocellulosic substrates—amaranth biomass and wheat bran—micromycete strains (*Trichoderma asperellum* and *Chaetomium globosum*) were cultivated on the surface of the substrate. The experiments were conducted under sterile conditions in 250 mL glass flasks.

In the first variant, 10 g of amaranth stems ground to a particle size of 0.2–0.5 cm were placed into flasks. In the second variant, a mixture consisting of 5 g of ground amaranth stems and 5 g of wheat bran was prepared. In both cases, the substrates were moistened to 50–60% with Mandels mineral nutrient medium (pH 5.5–5.7), brought to a solid-state medium condition, and sterilized.

The prepared substrates were inoculated with 3 mL of a suspension of micromycete strains previously cultivated in liquid Mandels nutrient medium and thoroughly mixed. Control variants consisted of substrates of the same composition without the addition of fungal suspension. All flasks were incubated under thermostatic conditions at 29–33°C. The experiments were conducted over a period of 15 days, during which the total protein content formed in the substrate was determined on a daily basis.

For protein extraction, 90 mL of distilled water or 2 M NaOH solution was added to the solid substrates colonized by fungi, and the samples were agitated on a shaker at 200 rpm for 1 hour. The mixture was then filtered through filter paper and prepared for analysis. Protein content was determined using the Lowry method. This method is based on the reaction of aromatic amino acids in proteins with the Folin reagent, resulting in the formation of a colored complex.

During the analysis, 0.5 mL of the test solution was mixed with 2.5 mL of reagent C (a mixture of 50 mL of reagent B and 1 mL of reagent A) and incubated for 10 minutes. Subsequently, 0.25 mL of reagent D was added, the mixture was thoroughly homogenized, and kept in the dark for 30 minutes. The intensity of the resulting color was measured at a wavelength of 750 nm using a spectrophotometer. The protein content was calculated based on a previously constructed calibration curve [13].

The chemical composition of the prepared feed was determined in accordance with GOST standards: 13496.3–93, 13496.14–87, 13496.4–93, 13496.2–91, 26570–95, 26657–97, 13496.1–98, 13496.12–98, and 13496.7–97.

Results and Discussion

As a result of the conducted experiments, the protein (biomass) production capacities of different fungal strains under solid-state fermentation conditions were compared. The obtained results demonstrated significant differences in the levels of protein synthesis among the studied strains, which were found to depend on their physiological and biochemical characteristics as well as their ability to utilize the substrate.

The highest value was recorded for *Chaetomium globosum*, which produced 10.8 mg/mL of protein. This result indicates the strong ability of this fungus to extensively degrade lignocellulosic substrates, efficiently assimilate carbon sources, and synthesize biomass intensively. It is well established that fungi of the genus *Chaetomium* possess a pronounced capacity to hydrolyze cellulose and hemicellulose components, whereby the resulting simple carbohydrates are rapidly converted into cellular biomass. Therefore, *Chaetomium globosum* can be considered a promising microorganism for feed protein production.

The next highest result was observed for *Trichoderma asperellum*, which produced 8.5 mg/mL of protein. This strain is distinguished by its high enzymatic activity, particularly its active synthesis of cellulase and xylanase enzymes. This facilitates rapid substrate degradation and accelerates the microbial assimilation of organic compounds in the nutrient medium. As a result, the nutrients required for biomass formation are generated more quickly. However, its biomass production level was slightly lower than that of *Chaetomium globosum*, which may be explained by the allocation of a portion of energy toward enzyme synthesis (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Protein synthesis by selected active strains, mg/mL (n = 4)

In *Trichoderma hamatum*, the protein content was 7.2 mg/mL, which can be considered a moderate level. Although this strain also exhibits cellulolytic properties, its enzymatic activity and biomass formation intensity were observed to be lower than those of *T. asperellum*. This may be associated with a relatively slower rate of substrate utilization and less intensive metabolic processes.

The lowest value was recorded for *Penicillium canescens*, which produced 6.1 mg/mL of protein. This strain is primarily known as a strong enzyme producer, particularly effective in the synthesis

of xylanase and cellulase enzymes. However, its capacity for biomass production is relatively low, which can be explained by the allocation of most of its energy toward enzyme synthesis. Therefore, *P. canescens* is more appropriately utilized not as a direct source of protein, but as an auxiliary microorganism for substrate degradation.

Overall, the obtained results indicate that the biological characteristics of fungi play a crucial role in the production of feed protein from lignocellulosic substrates under solid-state fermentation conditions. In particular, *Chaetomium globosum* is distinguished by its high biomass yield, whereas *Trichoderma asperellum* ensures rapid substrate degradation due to its strong enzymatic activity. Therefore, the combined application of these fungi may enhance bioconversion efficiency and enable the production of high-quality feed protein.

Degradation of Plant Residues by Fungi in Solid-State Media. Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is a widely cultivated agricultural crop characterized by high biomass production, and its stems and other residues represent lignocellulose-rich raw materials. The high content of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin in these residues limits their direct use as feed. Therefore, the enhancement of their nutritional value through microbiological processing is of significant scientific and practical importance.

In this study, for the purpose of feed protein production, a solid-state nutrient medium was prepared using ground corn stover mixed with wheat bran. The prepared substrates were inoculated with strains of *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Chaetomium globosum*, *Trichoderma hamatum*, and *Penicillium canescens*, previously cultivated in liquid Mandels medium at pH 5.5–6.5, and the fermentation process was carried out for 15 days.

During fermentation, the dynamics of protein synthesis were investigated, revealing that in all strains the protein content increased from the initial days of incubation, reached a maximum between days 5–10, and subsequently declined. According to the obtained results, the highest protein synthesis was recorded in *Chaetomium globosum*, with a maximum value of 71.2 ± 2.87 mg/g. This indicates the strong capacity of this strain to efficiently utilize lignocellulosic substrates and produce a high biomass yield.

Trichoderma asperellum also demonstrated high performance, with a maximum protein yield of 59.3 ± 2.24 mg/g. This strain exhibits strong enzymatic activity, and its ability to actively degrade cellulose and hemicellulose accelerates substrate utilization.

In *Trichoderma hamatum*, protein synthesis was at a moderate level, with a maximum value of 46.5 ± 2.17 mg/g. This indicates that the metabolic activity of this strain is somewhat lower compared to the other strains.

In *Penicillium canescens*, protein synthesis was relatively low, with a maximum value of 40.3 ± 1.81 mg/g. This can be explained by the fact that this fungus is primarily oriented toward enzyme production, while its capacity for biomass formation is limited.

It was also observed that protein synthesis was slightly higher in substrates prepared from a mixture of corn stover and wheat bran; however, no significant differences were recorded overall. This indicates that corn residues alone constitute a sufficient nutrient source for fungal growth and development. The strains produced 2.3–3 times more protein compared to the control (Table 1).

Table 1. Protein synthesis by active strains on plant residues (mg/g) (n = 6)

Days	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>	<i>Trichoderma hamatum</i>	<i>Penicillium canescens</i>
1	31,2±1,34	34,1±1,61	28,3±1,21	25,4±1,17

2	36,1±1,71	40,2±1,89	32,5±1,55	28,6±1,33
3	42,3±1,68	49,3±2,11	36,4±1,63	32,1±1,45
4	48,7±2,10	58,6±2,34	40,2±1,82	35,8±1,58
5	59,3±2,24	71,2±2,87	46,5±2,17	40,3±1,81
6	55,2±2,11	65,4±2,45	42,8±1,91	37,6±1,66
7	52,3±2,09	62,7±2,34	41,1±1,78	35,9±1,51
8	54,1±2,17	64,2±2,25	42,3±1,69	37,2±1,68
9	56,8±2,22	66,8±2,76	44,1±2,02	38,8±1,72
10	57,4±2,34	68,9±2,57	44,6±2,08	39,5±1,71
11	55,6±2,21	66,5±2,61	43,2±1,91	37,4±1,76
12	52,4±2,07	61,8±2,42	40,7±1,88	35,2±1,43
13	49,2±1,91	56,3±2,27	38,5±1,67	33,1±1,44
14	46,8±1,88	53,4±2,13	36,2±1,62	31,5±1,32
15	44,1±1,73	50,6±2,05	34,8±1,57	29,4±1,25
Contro 1	22,3±0,95	24,7±1,19	20,8±0,76	18,9±0,72

The table below presents the dynamics of protein synthesis (mg/g) by active fungal strains on plant residues over a 15-day period, clearly reflecting their activity in the bioconversion process.

According to the results, protein synthesis in all strains increased progressively from the initial days of incubation, reached a maximum between days 5–10, and subsequently showed a gradual decline. This trend can be explained by the depletion of readily degradable nutrients in the substrate and a corresponding reduction in metabolic activity.

The highest values were recorded for *Chaetomium globosum*. In this strain, protein content increased from 34.1±1.61 mg/g on day 1 to 71.2±2.87 mg/g on day 5, followed by a gradual decline to 50.6±2.05 mg/g by day 15. These results indicate the strong ability of this fungus to efficiently utilize lignocellulosic substrates and produce a high biomass yield.

In *Trichoderma asperellum*, similarly high results were observed, with protein synthesis increasing from 31.2±1.34 mg/g on day 1 to a maximum of 59.3±2.24 mg/g on day 5, followed by a gradual decline to 44.1±1.73 mg/g by day 15. The high enzymatic activity of this strain facilitated rapid substrate degradation, thereby positively influencing biomass formation.

In *Trichoderma hamatum*, protein synthesis was at a moderate level, reaching a maximum of 46.5±2.17 mg/g on day 5. In the subsequent days, this value gradually declined. This indicates that the metabolic activity and substrate utilization rate of this strain are somewhat lower compared to the other strains.

In *Penicillium canescens*, the lowest level of protein synthesis was recorded, with a maximum value of 40.3±1.81 mg/g on day 5. This can be attributed to the fact that this strain is primarily oriented toward enzyme production, resulting in a comparatively lower capacity for biomass formation.

In the control variant, all values were significantly lower (18.9–24.7 mg/g), confirming that protein accumulation in the substrate proceeds at a much slower rate in the absence of fungal involvement.

The obtained results indicate that under solid-state fermentation conditions, *Chaetomium globosum* is the most efficient strain in terms of biomass (protein) production, while *Trichoderma*

asperellum is distinguished by its high enzymatic activity. Therefore, the combined application of these strains appears promising for the efficient bioconversion of lignocellulosic substrates and the production of high-quality feed protein.

Chemical Composition of Feed Obtained from Microbiologically Treated Corn Stover. Corn stover is a lignocellulose-rich raw material with low nutritional value. It contains high levels of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, components that are not fully digestible in the animal organism. Therefore, improving the nutritional value of such plant residues through microbiological processing is of significant scientific and practical importance.

In this study, locally isolated and identified strains of *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Penicillium canescens*, and *Chaetomium globosum* were used. These strains were selected based on their ability to degrade lignocellulosic substrates and their enzymatic activity.

During the experiment, microbiological treatment was applied to substrates prepared from corn stover as well as mixtures of corn stover and wheat bran. The results demonstrated that all strains were capable of degrading cellulose and hemicellulose; however, their efficiencies differed.

In terms of enzymatic activity, *Penicillium canescens* exhibited the highest performance, particularly demonstrating superiority in the synthesis of xylanase and endo-1,4- β -glucanase enzymes. This indicates its strong capacity for the extensive degradation of lignocellulosic substrates.

Trichoderma asperellum was distinguished by the stability and complexity of its enzymatic activity, demonstrating the ability to efficiently hydrolyze both cellulose and hemicellulose simultaneously. This strain enables balanced substrate degradation and ensures the stable progression of the bioconversion process.

Although the enzymatic activity of *Chaetomium globosum* was relatively lower, it is notable for its strong ability to utilize lignocellulosic substrates and its high biomass production capacity. This indicates its important role in the process of feed protein production.

Overall, the obtained results indicate that each strain plays a specific role in the efficient bioconversion of lignocellulosic plant residues: *Penicillium canescens* ensures intensive enzymatic degradation, *Trichoderma asperellum* provides stable and complex hydrolysis, while *Chaetomium globosum* contributes to biomass accumulation and protein production.

Therefore, the application of these strains either individually or in combination ensures the efficient degradation of lignocellulosic substrates and enables the production of products with high nutritional value (Table 2).

Table 2. Chemical composition of feed obtained through microbiological treatment

Determined parameters	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	<i>Penicillium canescens</i>	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>	Control (corn stover)
Ash	12,30	13,40	10,60	9,86
Nitrogen	2,65	1,45	2,95	1,1
Protein	16,60	9,20	18,50	10,81
Fat	2,30	1,05	2,80	1,41
Fiber	33,80	40,50	25,90	34,12
Nitrogen-free extractives (NFE)	34,50	35,40	41,80	45,07
Feed units	0.62	0.52	0.86	0,45

Total energy value, kcal/kg	2880	2250	3182	2200
Calcium	2,35	1.77	1.61	1.25
Phosphorus	0.80	0.22	1,10	0.67
Acidity	0.8 ⁰	3.4 ⁰	0.7 ⁰	5.8 ⁰
Toxicity	Non-toxic	Non-toxic	Non-toxic	Non-toxic

Changes in the chemical composition of feed obtained after the microbiological treatment of corn stover using *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Penicillium canescens*, and *Chaetomium globosum* are presented. The results demonstrate that the microbiological bioconversion process significantly enhances the nutritional value of the feed.

According to the analysis results, an increase in protein content compared to the control was observed in all experimental variants. In particular, the highest value was recorded for *Chaetomium globosum*, with a protein content of 18.50%. This can be explained by its strong ability to efficiently utilize lignocellulosic substrates and produce high biomass. In *Trichoderma asperellum*, the protein content was also high (16.60%), indicating its capacity to effectively degrade the substrate through a complex enzymatic system. In contrast, *Penicillium canescens* showed a relatively lower protein content (9.20%), which can be attributed to its primary orientation toward enzyme production.

Significant differences were observed in fiber content. The lowest value was recorded in *Chaetomium globosum* (25.90%), confirming its strong ability to actively degrade lignocellulose. In *Trichoderma asperellum*, this parameter was at a moderate level (33.80%), whereas the highest value was observed in *Penicillium canescens* (40.50%). This can be explained by the specialization of this strain in producing enzymes that primarily degrade hemicellulose, while not fully decomposing lignin and complex cellulose components. The high fiber content in the control variant (34.12%) indicates the lack of degradation of the raw lignocellulosic substrate.

An increase in nitrogen-free extractives (NFE) also confirms the breakdown of complex polysaccharides into simple carbohydrates as a result of enzymatic hydrolysis. The highest NFE content was recorded in *Chaetomium globosum* (41.80%). Although the control variant showed a higher NFE value (45.07%), this is associated with the presence of soluble carbohydrates, while the overall nutritional value remains low.

The energy value and feed unit indicators were also significantly improved. The highest energy content was observed in *Chaetomium globosum* (3182 kcal/kg), demonstrating its superiority in enhancing feed quality. In *Trichoderma asperellum*, the energy value reached 2880 kcal/kg, indicating a favorable result. In contrast, *Penicillium canescens* showed a relatively lower energy value (2250 kcal/kg), which can be attributed to its lower biomass production capacity. The control variant had an energy value of 2200 kcal/kg, reflecting the low digestibility of lignocellulose.

An increase in mineral components, particularly calcium and phosphorus, indicates enhanced bioavailability as a result of microbiological treatment. Notably, a higher calcium content was recorded in *Trichoderma asperellum* (2.35%), while *Chaetomium globosum* showed the highest phosphorus content (1.10%).

Regarding acidity, a relatively higher value was observed in *Penicillium canescens* (3.40), which can be attributed to the formation of organic acids during the fermentation process. In the other strains, acidity remained at a lower level.

The absence of toxic substances in all variants indicates that the obtained product is safe for livestock use.

The obtained results demonstrate that microbiological treatment significantly enhances the nutritional value of corn stover. In particular, *Chaetomium globosum* exhibited the highest efficiency in terms of protein and energy parameters, while *Trichoderma asperellum* was distinguished by its balanced bioconversion performance. Despite its high enzymatic activity, *Penicillium canescens* showed comparatively lower results in biomass production.

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